

1 The genetics of adaptation in freshwater Eurasian shad (*Alosa*)

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39 **Abstract**

40 Studying the genetics of phenotypic convergence can yield important insights into
41 adaptive evolution. Here, we conducted a comparative genomic study of four lineages
42 (species and subspecies) of anadromous shad (*Alosa*) that have independently evolved
43 life cycles entirely completed in freshwater. Three naturally diverged (*A. fallax lacustris*,
44 *A. f. killarnensis*, and *A. macedonica*) and the fourth (*A. alosa*) was artificially landlocked
45 during the last century. To conduct this analysis, we assembled and annotated a draft of
46 the *A. alosa* genome and generated whole-genome sequencing for 16 anadromous and
47 freshwater populations of shad. Widespread evidence for parallel genetic changes in
48 freshwater populations within lineages was found. In freshwater *A. alosa*, which have
49 only been diverging for tens of generations, this shows that parallel adaptive evolution
50 can rapidly occur. However, parallel genetic changes across lineages were comparatively
51 rare. The degree of genetic parallelism was not strongly related to the number of shared
52 polymorphisms between lineages, thus suggesting that other factors such as divergence
53 among ancestral populations or environmental variation may influence genetic
54 parallelism across these lineages. These overall patterns were exemplified by genetic
55 differentiation involving a paralog of *ATPase-a1* that appears to be under selection in just
56 two of the more distantly related lineages studied, *A. f. lacustris* and *A. alosa*. Our
57 findings provide insights into the tempo and genetic architecture of adaptation along a
58 continuum of population divergence.

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61 **Keywords:** phenotypic convergence, parallel evolution, adaptation, genomics, whole-
62 genome pool-seq

63 **Introduction**

64 Organisms often evolve similar phenotypes to adapt to ecological changes or
65 expand their niches (Endler, 1986). When such phenotypic convergence occurs,
66 analogous selective forces are often involved. However, the extent to which identical, or
67 related genetic alternations (i.e., “parallel”) are responsible for phenotypic convergence
68 varies greatly both within and across taxa (Bailey et al., 2015; Oke et al., 2017; Perrier et
69 al., 2013; Stern, 2013). While our understanding of parallelism has progressed in recent
70 years, a general understanding of the ecological and evolutionary circumstances initiating
71 its occurrence remains elusive (Losos, 2011; Stern, 2013; Storz, 2016).

72 The likelihood of parallel evolution can depend on several factors. In the absence
73 of gene flow, unless populations share advantageous polymorphisms, parallelism is
74 dependent upon the same, or similar, alleles arising via de novo mutation within each
75 newly colonized location or ecological setting (Colosimo et al., 2005). This can take
76 hundreds or thousands of generations in higher organisms like vertebrates (Hoban et al.,
77 2016). Thus, selection upon existing shared polymorphism is usually the most likely way
78 for parallelism to arise. This hypothesis has been supported by studies on a variety of
79 species, including stickleback (Colosimo et al., 2005; Nelson & Cresko, 2018; Oke et al.,
80 2017), cod (Bradbury et al., 2010), and herring (Lamichhaney et al., 2017). However,
81 since ecological adaptation involves an ecological shift, alleles for relevant fitness-related
82 traits may be slightly deleterious, or under balancing selection, within the ancestral
83 setting. Consequently, such alleles will tend to segregate at low or intermediate
84 frequencies in ancestral lineages (Chevin et al., 2010). This lowers the probability that
85 they will be present in newly founded populations, and when existent, it increases the

86 chance that they will be lost due to genetic drift.

87 Gene flow can promote parallelism by increasing levels of shared polymorphism
88 (Stuart et al., 2017). However, gene flow can also have mixed effects on the rate and
89 direction of adaptive divergence. The ultimate consequences of gene flow may depend on
90 factors including the intensity and consistency of selection, the genetic architecture of the
91 trait (Garcia-Ramos & Kirkpatrick, 1997; Star & Spencer, 2013), and interactions among
92 the genes involved (Chevin et al., 2010). In addition, when multiple alleles with similar
93 phenotypic effects are present, the likelihood of nonparallel evolution can increase by
94 chance alone (Stern, 2013), or for other reasons such as subtle differences in spatially
95 varying selection pressure (Conte et al., 2012; Frickel et al., 2018). Indeed, selection due
96 to environmental variation has been found to influence parallelism in several species
97 including stickleback (Hohenlohe et al., 2010), cichlid fish (Elmer et al., 2014), whitefish
98 (Gagnaire et al., 2013), stick-insects (Soria-Carrasco et al., 2014), stickleback
99 (Raeymaekers et al., 2017; Stuart et al., 2017) and marine snails (Morales et al., 2019).
100 Due to the range of factors that can affect the likelihood of parallelism, it is now widely
101 accepted that it will only occur in specific circumstances.

102 To further our understanding of these topics, we studied the genetics of adaptation
103 in four independent lineages of Eurasian shad (aloses; genus *Alosa*) (Linck, 1790) that
104 are typically anadromous, but also include populations with a completely freshwater life
105 history (Figure 1, Supplemental Table 1). These aloses are an extraordinary model
106 system for studying parallelism for several reasons. Firstly, phenotypic differences
107 between freshwater and anadromous shad are usually similar and involve traits known to
108 have a genetic basis in other fish species, including size, parity, and numbers of gill

109 rakers (Aprahamian et al., 2003). Secondly, having diverged from each other less than 1.5
110 million years ago, the Eurasian shad are closely related lineages (Faria et al., 2012).
111 Lastly, the alosine model enables us to study the genetics of adaptation in populations
112 that have diverged in different ways. For example, while the freshwater *A. alosa* we
113 studied were all artificially landlocked in reservoirs in Portugal during the last century
114 and evolved without gene flow (Aprahamian et al., 2003; Pereira et al., 1999), the
115 freshwater populations of three of the lineages (species and subspecies) we examined
116 inhabit lakes in Italy (*A. f. lacustris*), Ireland (*A. f. killarnensis*) and Greece (*A.*
117 *macedonica*) and naturally diverged sometime during the last 30 thousand years after the
118 retreat of the last Pleistocene glaciers (Coscia et al., 2013; Faria et al., 2012). The
119 phenotypic changes observed in these freshwater shad appear to reflect this difference in
120 divergence time. Specifically, while freshwater shad in all four lineages have experienced
121 a sharp decrease in body size (Aprahamian et al., 2003; Pereira et al., 1999), it has been
122 least dramatic in *A. alosa*. Additionally, within *A. alosa*, individuals belonging to the
123 oldest freshwater population (~75 years) are the smallest of the three lineages that exist,
124 suggesting the adaptive process is ongoing in this lineage. Studying the evolution of these
125 freshwater shads is therefore an excellent opportunity to gain insight into the factors that
126 influence parallelism including the phylogenetic and temporal scales at which it occurs
127 and the impacts of gene flow.

128 In this study, we generated a de novo genome assembly for *A. alosa* and
129 conducted whole-genome resequencing to identify loci that may be under natural
130 selection in freshwater populations of shad. The resulting data was then used to determine
131 if parallel genetic evolution may have occurred within or across the lineages studied.

132 Here, “parallel evolution” or “parallelism” refers to allele frequency changes in the same
133 gene or genomic region, but not necessarily the same mutation. Loci involved in
134 adaptation to freshwater in these lineages were identified by searching for genomic
135 regions with extraordinary differences in allele frequencies between anadromous and
136 freshwater populations. Such genome scans have yielded some of the most influential
137 insights into the genetic architecture of adaptation and speciation (Alves et al., 2019;
138 Cresko et al., 2004; Jones et al., 2012; Losos, 1998; Nachman et al., 2003; Vitti et al.,
139 2013). However, since neutral genetic changes can result in patterns of allele frequencies
140 that are similar to those caused by natural selection, (Ralph & Coop, 2010), genome
141 scans can yield false-positive results. To help avoid this pitfall, we separately analyzed
142 each lineage. Given what is known about rapid evolution and adaptation to freshwater in
143 other anadromous species, we expected that parallelism would be positively related to the
144 amount of polymorphism shared between lineages, and the lowest in *A. alosa*.

145

146 **Materials and Methods**

147 *Genome assembly and annotation*

148 Blood and muscle tissue were taken from a single freshwater *A. alosa* caught in
149 the Aguieira Reservoir, Portugal by a local fisherman and stored on ice for several hours
150 until it could be placed at -80C for long-term storage. DNA was extracted from blood or
151 tissue from the specimen caught using EasySpin™ 96-well extraction plates according to
152 the manufacturer’s recommendations except that vortexing the DNA was avoided to
153 minimize shearing. DNA from multiple extractions was concentrated to satisfy the
154 requirements of the following sequencing library methods.

155 The Allis shad (*A. alosa*) genome was assembled using a combination of data
156 from short read and mate-pair sequencing libraries. For contig building, one 250bp insert
157 library with overlapping reads (2x150 bp paired-end) was generated using Illumina
158 paired-end chemistry (V2) and run on three lanes of an Illumina MiSeq 2500. Scaffolding
159 was accomplished with mate-pair libraries (insert sizes 3 kilobases (kb), 5 kb, 7 kb, and
160 10 kb) made using the Nextera Mate-Pair Library Preparation Kit (Illumina). The mate-
161 pair libraries were multiplexed and run together on three lanes of an Illumina HiSeq
162 1500. In addition, a 20 kb mate-pair dataset was generated by Lucigen Corporation
163 (USA). The *A. alosa* genome was assembled using ALLPATHS-LG-52488 (Butler et al.,
164 2008). ALLPATHS-LG-52488 was run with default settings with the exception that the
165 HAPLOIDIFY option was engaged. To determine the optimal coverage of short-read,
166 overlapping sequence data for the Allis genome assembly using ALLPATHS-LG-52488,
167 the assembly was run using from 40X to 60X coverage at 5X increments, and the
168 coverage that resulted in the greatest contig N50, 55X, was used for the final assembly.

169 The genome assembly was annotated by analysis of sequence composition and by
170 generating ab initio gene models using transcriptome and protein data. All software for
171 the annotation was run using default parameters unless otherwise specified. Repeat
172 regions were identified and masked using RepeatMasker (Tarailo-Graovac & Chen,
173 2009) with an *A. alosa*-specific repeat library that was generated for our de novo shad
174 genome using RepeatModeler (<http://www.repeatmasker.org/RepeatModeler/>) and
175 RepBase23.02. Intron/exon boundaries were inferred by aligning RNA-seq data
176 generated from liver, muscle, and gill tissue types (see Supplemental Methods) to our
177 shad genome using Hisat2 (Kim et al., 2019). The aligned RNA reads were used to obtain

178 a genome-guided transcriptome assembly using Cufflinks (v2.2.1) (Trapnell et al., 2012).
179 An initial run of Maker2 (Holt & Yandell, 2011) was conducted on the repeat-masked
180 genome using the output from Cufflinks, a publicly available transcriptome assembly for
181 *A. alosa* based on RNAseq data from ten tissue types (Pasquier et al., 2016) and high-
182 confidence protein sequence evidence from the Uniprot Swiss-Prot and Uniprot *Danio*
183 *reio* databases. The genome was then re-annotated with *Maker2* using gene models
184 generated with GeneMark-ES (Lomsadze et al. 2005). To characterize the biological
185 functions of the expected transcripts of each gene model and retrieve PFAM and GO
186 terms we used Sma3s (Casimiro-Soriguer et al. 2017). Transcripts were also compared to
187 the Uniprot protein databases mentioned earlier using BLASTp (v2.2.28+), and tRNAs
188 were identified using tRNAscan-SE-2.0 (Lowe & Eddy, 1997). Finally, SnpEff (v.3.4;
189 Cingolani et al.,2014) was used to annotate variants and classify them as non-
190 synonymous, synonymous, UTR, 5 kb upstream, 5 kb downstream, intronic or intergenic.
191 Assembly and annotation completeness was quantified by the number of conserved
192 single-copy orthologs present both in the reference sequence and in the annotation using
193 the Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs (BUSCO) software (v. 3) with the
194 Actinopterygii_odb9 standard dataset (Simão et al., 2015).

195

196 *Allele frequencies of SNP loci*

197 Allele frequencies of SNP loci for use in population analysis and genome scans
198 were estimated using a pooled DNA sequencing approach. Muscle, fin, liver, or blood
199 was taken from 467, adult anadromous and freshwater shad caught in each location by
200 commercial fishermen or angling from 1991 to 2015 (Figure 1; Supplemental Table 1).

201 All anadromous individuals sampled were caught in rivers or streams as they migrated
202 upstream to spawn. Tissue samples were preserved in 95% ethanol or placed on ice and
203 then stored at -80°C. DNA was extracted from tissue samples using EasySpin™ 96-well
204 extraction plates according to the manufacturer's recommendations. Eurasian shad can
205 naturally hybridize (Arahamian et al., 2003; Taillebois et al., 2019). To avoid including
206 any hybrids in the pools, the individuals used for them were prescreened using
207 microsatellite markers as described in Sabatino et al. 2022. For each of the 16 sampling
208 locations, pooled DNA samples were made from 100 nanograms of DNA per individual.
209 Each of the 16 pools was then tagged with a unique Nextera sequence tag and prepared
210 for sequencing using paired-end (2 x 125bp) Illumina chemistry. The pooled DNA
211 libraries were sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq 1500 to an effective coverage from 24x to
212 46x per pool with an average of 32x (Supplemental Table 1). The resulting reads were
213 trimmed with Trimmomatic version 0.32 (Bolger et al., 2014) with the following settings:
214 illuminaclip:Tru-Seq2-PE.fa:2:30:10 slidingwindow:4:20 leading:10 trailing:10 crop:101
215 headcrop:0 minlen:80. FASTQC v10.1 (Babraham Bioinformatics) was then run to check
216 the data overall for base and sequence quality.

217 The pool-seq data was then used to estimate allele frequencies for SNP loci in
218 each of the four lineages (Figure 1) studied. First, the trimmed pool-seq datasets were
219 mapped to our *A. alosa* genome assembly using BWA-MEM (Li & Durbin, 2009) with
220 default settings, followed by local realignment performed using GATK
221 RealignerTargetCreator and IndelRealigner options (McKenna et al., 2010). An initial set
222 of DNA sequence variants was then identified using Samtools mpileup, (Li et al., 2009).
223 The set of variants identified using Samtools was filtered with the Perl script

224 mpileup2sync.pl of Popoolation2 (Kofler et al., 2011) with the following settings: base
225 quality (Q20), minimum count of the minor allele set to four, minimum coverage of 10,
226 and maximum coverage set at twice the genome-wide average (per population). The
227 resulting set of SNP loci was further filtered by removing those not identified as biallelic
228 variants, and retaining only SNPs with an overall quality score greater than 20 using
229 FreeBayes v0.9.21 (Garrison & Marth, 2012) with the following set of parameters: use-
230 best-n-alleles 4, pooled-discrete, min-coverage 10, min-repeat-entropy 1, min-mapping-
231 quality 60, min-base-quality 20, use-mapping-quality, max-coverage 100. FreeBayes was
232 run separately for each of the four lineages studied (Figure 1; Supplemental Table 1). In
233 addition, SNP loci located within 10bp from an insertion or deletion as identified by
234 FreeBayes were filtered from the final dataset. Allele frequencies for the filtered set of
235 SNP loci were then calculated for each population using Popoolation2 with “pool size”
236 set to twice the number of individuals in each pool as suggested for diploid organisms.

237

238 *Genome scans for loci under selection*

239 Loci that may have been influenced by natural selection were identified using a
240 sliding window analysis of the change in allele frequencies of SNP loci (ΔAF) between
241 anadromous and freshwater populations within each of the four lineages described in the
242 previous section. To reduce the effect of population history, ΔAF estimates were
243 standardized by subtracting each from the genome-wide mean (per lineage) and then
244 dividing by the standard deviation. Allele frequency differences between all possible
245 pairs of anadromous and freshwater populations within each lineage were then averaged.
246 Finally, a sliding window approach was used where genomic windows were defined as

247 the average ΔAF for 20 consecutive SNP loci along each scaffold and calculated every 10
248 SNPs (i.e., step size). To avoid high error rates associated with smaller scaffolds enriched
249 with repetitive sequences, windows were only calculated for the largest 1000 scaffolds,
250 which physically covered 813Mb or 91% of the *A. alosa* genome.

251 The statistical significance of extreme values of average ΔAF in each lineage was
252 then evaluated using permutations. In each permutation, populations were randomly
253 assigned as anadromous or landlocked, and then the ΔAF for each SNP window was
254 calculated as described earlier with the exception that the starting location to begin
255 counting consecutive SNPs was randomly chosen to range from 1 to 20, which allows for
256 all possible window combinations of 20-SNP windows to be sampled. A thousand
257 permutations were conducted per lineage. Significant ΔAF can be a consequence of
258 divergent selection or genetic hitchhiking (Lewontin & Krakauer, 1973). Since the
259 freshwater populations studied have been diverging for different lengths of time (tens to
260 thousands of generations), and for comparative purposes, we conducted permutation tests
261 to identify outliers using two different thresholds (99th and 99.9th percentiles). We
262 considered genomic windows with ΔAF in the 99th and 99.9th percentiles (i.e., the top 1%
263 and top 0.1%, respectively) as outliers or “candidate” targets of natural selection.
264 Depending on factors including recombination and hitchhiking, some genomic windows
265 with extreme ΔAF that neighbored each other may have been caused by selection on the
266 same locus or gene. Based on this, and given our aim to gain a more conservative
267 estimate of the number of candidate loci, we merged outlier windows within 20 kb of
268 each other and referred to them together with outlier windows as “genomic outlier
269 regions”. Genes neighboring outlier regions within 20 kb were considered possible

270 targets of natural selection and are reported.

271 To evaluate the ΔAF method we used, we also conducted genomic scans on each
272 of the four lineages using PCadapt (Luu et al., 2016). PCadapt was run with default
273 parameters for pool datasets except that the minimum minor allele frequency was set to 0.
274 For consistency, PCadapt was run using the same genomic windows as evaluated in our
275 ΔAF analysis.

276

277 *Population Genetics*

278 We used three population genetic statistics (D_{XY} , Tajima's D, and π) to analyze
279 our pool-seq data with two main goals in mind. Firstly, we tested if patterns of D_{XY} and
280 Tajima's D in non-outlier (neutral) and outlier regions identified at the 99.9th percentile
281 cutoff level showed signatures of natural selection. For these comparisons, Tajima's D
282 was examined separately in each of the 16 populations studied, while D_{XY} was averaged
283 across all anadromous-landlocked population pairs per lineage. Secondly, previous
284 research has shown that mutations maintained by natural selection sometimes segregate
285 in large haplotypes (Martinez Barrio et al., 2016; Nelson & Cresko, 2018; Schluter &
286 Conte, 2009). To test if our data fit this expectation, we estimated π for each life history
287 type within each lineage (see Supplemental Methods).

288

289 *Parallelism within and among lineages*

290 We studied parallelism within the only two lineages in our study that have
291 multiple freshwater populations, *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* (Figure 1). To measure
292 parallelism within them, we calculated the percentage of outlier regions shared by each

293 pair and the set of three freshwater populations within each of them. This required us to
294 identify outlier regions in each freshwater population of *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*,
295 which we accomplished using the same ΔAF methods as described above (99th
296 percentile). Similarly, pairwise comparisons of outlier regions in populations from
297 different lineages were conducted. We then estimated the amount of polymorphism
298 shared by each pair of lineages. For this analysis, and throughout the text, a polymorphic
299 site refers to any SNP we found using our methods above that was variable, or fixed for
300 an alternative allele, in at least one of the populations (anadromous or freshwater) studied
301 in a given lineage. Since the total number of SNP loci per lineage varied, we calculated
302 the average of the percentage of SNPs shared in each lineage of the pair being examined.
303 To help understand patterns of parallelism, we then compared the percentage of outlier
304 regions shared by populations to the percentage of polymorphism common between their
305 respective lineages.

306 Lastly, to help visualize patterns of genetic convergence across lineages, we
307 generated heat maps of ΔAF for all outlier windows. One heat map was made per lineage.
308 Specifically, for each ΔAF window in the 99.9th percentile of the target lineage, the
309 average ΔAF for all SNPs in the same genomic window in each of the other three
310 lineages was calculated. If the corresponding genomic window had fewer than two SNPs
311 it was excluded from the analysis.

312

313 *Patterns of genetic convergence in ATPase- $\alpha 1$*

314 To explore patterns of parallel genetic evolution in these lineages in greater detail
315 we focused our investigation on ATPase genes that are known to be under selection in

316 fish species (Wong et al., 2016), including alosines (Leguen et al., 2007; Velotta et al.,
317 2017), and were outliers in our analysis. We began by using phylogenetic analysis to
318 establish the orthology relationships of ATPase- $\alpha 1$ identified in our *A. alosa* genome
319 assembly. Studying comprehensive sets of gene copies from both closely related and
320 moderately divergent species relative to the ingroup can increase accuracy when using
321 phylogenetic methods to infer orthology (Gabaldón, 2008). Thus, most of the sequences
322 used for the phylogeny were coding region DNA from two species for which highly
323 complete genomic resources exist, the zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) and a clupeid (like *Alosa*),
324 Atlantic herring (*Clupea harengus*). Sequences of alewife (*A. pseudoharengus*) and
325 several outgroups were also included (see Supplemental Table 2 for the sources of all
326 sequences). These sequences were aligned using CLUSTAL X (Larkin et al., 2007) using
327 default parameters, and phylogenetic analysis was conducted using the maximum-
328 likelihood (ML) method with RAXML software version 7.2.7 (Stamatakis et al., 2012).
329 In each analysis, RAXML was set to choose the best-fit models of nucleotide or protein
330 substitution. The ML phylogenetic tree was reconstructed from 1000 RAXML runs,
331 followed by 1000 bootstrap replicates.

332 To investigate the potential importance of three nonsynonymous substitutions in
333 *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.1b* that were found to have significant Δ AF between anadromous and
334 freshwater *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* we used protein modeling and phylogenetic
335 methods. Following (Dalziel et al., 2014), the protein model used, PDB 2ZXE, was the
336 crystal structure of dogfish (*Squalus acanthias*) (Linnaeus, 1758) Na⁺, K⁺ ATPase bound
337 to K⁺ and MgF₄₋₂ (Shinoda et al., 2009). The model was visualized using CCP4MG
338 v.2.10.10 (<http://www.ccp4.ac.uk>). To measure how phylogenetically conserved each

339 amino acid site is across fish species, we aligned the protein sequences for all ATPase-
340 $\alpha 1$ found in the *A. alosa* genome annotation and several other fish highly divergent
341 species listed in Supplemental Table 3. Finally, to help understand the significance of the
342 ΔAF estimate for the nonsynonymous mutation in *ATPase- $\alpha 1.1b$* shared by *A. alosa* and
343 *A. f. lacustris* (67614/968), we counted the number of cases where any nonsynonymous
344 mutation shared by *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* was also in the top 95th percentile of ΔAF
345 (per site) between anadromous and freshwater populations in each lineage.

346

347 **Results**

348 *Genome Assembly and Annotation*

349 To allow us to conduct genome-wide scans for candidate loci in freshwater shad
350 we generated a draft genome of *A. alosa* using short-read and mate-pair DNA data from a
351 single, wild-caught individual using the ALLPATHS-LG-52488 assembler. The size of
352 the *A. alosa* genome was estimated to be 889Mb using the k-mer method (Table 1). The
353 resulting genome assembly, as measured by the total length of all scaffolds greater than
354 1000bp, was 876 Mb, indicating that it represents 98% of the entire genome. However,
355 only 64% of the genome assembly was comprised of sequence data, with gaps making up
356 the remaining 36%. The contig N50 of the assembled genome was short (9.9 Kb). Given
357 that 36% of the genome was estimated to be repetitive sequences (Table 1), and the limits
358 of short-read sequence data for resolving repeat regions (Butler et al., 2008), the short
359 contig N50 was likely due to repetitive sequences being well distributed throughout the
360 shad genome. Scaffolding resulted in an assembly with an N50 of 2.03Mb, indicating that
361 the mate-pair data was informative for bridging contigs. Our annotation of the *A. alosa*

362 genome assembly yielded 22,993 gene models. The BUSCO analysis of our annotation
363 indicated that out of 4584 gene models tested, 71.5% were present and complete (66.0%
364 single-copy and 5.5% duplicated) and 11.3% present and incomplete, leaving 17.2%
365 missing. While the assembly was sufficiently complete to identify hundreds of candidate
366 regions in each lineage, a significant proportion of loci involved in adaption may have
367 been missed.

368

369 *Whole-genome sequencing and genome scans for candidate loci*

370 A crucial assumption of our tests for parallelism is that the lineages and
371 populations studied have independently adapted to freshwater. Our phylogenetic analysis
372 (Figure 1b), and previous work (Faria et al. 2012) make it clear that the lineages studied
373 evolved independently. The freshwater populations of *A. alosa* we examined were all
374 founded after being trapped behind dams built in unconnected drainages during the past
375 century (Aprahamian et al., 2003), and their independence has been confirmed by genetic
376 analysis here, and more comprehensively in (Faria et al., 2012; Sabatino et al., 2022). The
377 evolutionary history of the Italian lake populations examined, however, is less clear. Our
378 analysis is consistent with previous work showing they all were founded by anadromous
379 individuals in the Po River and therefore are closely related (Faria et al. 2012, Sabatino et
380 al. 2022). The geologic record suggests that each of the lakes that these freshwater *A. f.*
381 *lacustris* now inhabit, and the rivers into which they flow, were not directly connected
382 during or after the Pleistocene (Castaldini et al., 2019). However, given their close
383 relationship, and that post-colonization gene flow among them was possible, these
384 freshwater populations may not be independent. Accordingly, the statistical approach

385 used to conduct genome scans for outlier loci does not assume independence among
386 freshwater populations within lineages (see below).

387 To study parallelism we conducted whole-genome resequencing of pools of DNA
388 (“pool-seq”) from 16 populations of shad representing four different lineages of *Alosa*.
389 This included generating pool-seq data for at least two anadromous, and from one, or
390 three, freshwater populations, per lineage. The pool-seq data was then used to estimate
391 allele frequencies for SNP loci that were then used for population genetic analysis. The
392 highest number of SNPs was found in the *A. f. killarnensis* lineage (~1.9M),
393 approximately two to three times higher than the other three lineages (*A. alosa* ~ 0.6M; *A.*
394 *f. lacustris* ~ 0.8M; *A. macedonica*: ~ 0.9M) (Supplemental Table 1, 4).

395 Allele frequencies for the resulting SNP loci were then used to conduct genome
396 scans for candidate loci in each of the four lineages studied using a sliding window
397 approach and permutation tests. The effect of natural selection on SNP allele frequencies
398 can be highly variable even when selection is strong (Wilson et al., 2014). We conducted
399 permutation tests to identify outliers using two different statistical thresholds (99th and
400 99.9th percentiles) (Figure 2; Table 2; Supplemental Text; Supplemental Table 5). To try
401 to avoid over-estimating the number of candidate genomic locations identified in our
402 genome scans, and help identify overlapping outlier regions in different lineages, outlier
403 windows within 20 kilobases of each other were merged into outlier genomic regions.
404 This resulted in a roughly two to a six-fold reduction in the number of genomic areas
405 identified as candidates (Table 2).

406 Genes in the outlier regions identified in each lineage have a variety of biological
407 functions including osmoregulation, apoptosis, stress response, metabolism, brain and

408 eye development, muscle growth, and immunity (Supplemental Figure 1; Supplemental
409 Table 5; see Supplemental Text), some of which had previously been shown to be
410 involved in adaptation to osmotic stress or life history changes in *Alosa* or other fish
411 species (e.g. *ATPase- α 1* (Velotta et al., 2017); *IMPA2* (Gardell et al., 2013)). Candidate
412 genes were often in locations with relatively low genetic diversity (Supplemental Figure
413 2), further supporting the hypothesis that they are under selection.

414 To evaluate our Δ AF method for conducting genomic scans we used PCadapt.
415 The number of population clusters (k) per lineage identified using PCadapt and used for
416 the outlier analysis was two in all cases except for *A. alosa* where four better fit the data
417 (Supplemental Figure 3). The percentage of outlier windows identified in our Δ AF
418 analysis that overlapped with those found using PCadapt ranged 75 to 100 percent (99.9th
419 percentile in the Δ AF analysis) and 57 to 89 percent (99th percentile) (Supplemental
420 Table 6; Supplemental Figure 4), indicating a generally high level of congruence between
421 the two methods. Differences between them were likely attributable to how population
422 structure impacts the results of each method. For example, in the PCadapt analysis of the
423 *A. f. lacustris* lineage, one of the main drivers of differentiation in the first component is
424 the genetic distance between the two anadromous populations studied, which may have
425 diluted the signal from contrasts between them and the freshwater populations examined.
426 While our Δ AF analysis is also impacted by neutral evolutionary history, it was designed
427 to minimize its effect and to identify outliers specifically associated with adapting to a
428 completely freshwater life cycle. Additionally, based on the several-fold greater number
429 of outlier windows identified using PCadapt (Supplemental Table 6), our Δ AF method is
430 the more conservative of the two. We, therefore, note outlier regions that were identified

431 by both methods (Supplemental Table 5) but conducted our full analysis of parallelism
432 using the results of our ΔAF outlier analysis.

433

434 *Population Genetics*

435 We studied each lineage using D_{XY} , Tajima's D, and π . Divergence (D_{XY})
436 between anadromous and freshwater populations was consistently higher in outlier
437 regions compared to non-outlier ones in all four lineages (Supplemental Figure 6a). Mean
438 Tajima's D was below zero in all 16 populations examined (Supplemental Figure 7),
439 suggesting they may have experienced range expansions, as was found for several of the
440 populations studied here using mtDNA data (Faria et al., 2012). Bias in our estimation of
441 rare alleles, which can occur using pool-seq data (Nielsen et al., 2012), may also have
442 contributed to low estimates of Tajima's D. Tajima's D were significantly lower in
443 outlier regions in *A. f. lacustris*, *A. f. killarnensis*, and *A. macedonica*, but not in *A. alosa*
444 except for one of the anadromous populations examined, where the opposite trend was
445 found. The different pattern in Tajima's D found for *A. alosa* than the other three lineages
446 could be due to the young age of its freshwater populations (tens of generations), as they
447 are unlikely to be at genetic equilibrium. Nonetheless, the observed patterns of Tajima's
448 D in all three naturally occurring lineages, and those for D_{XY} for all four of them, suggest
449 that the outlier regions examined are targets of natural selection.

450 Differences in π within and outside of outlier regions were detected in five of the
451 eight comparisons we conducted (Supplemental Figure 7b). In *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*,
452 outlier regions in both anadromous and freshwater populations showed a significant
453 excess in diversity when compared with neutral ones, suggesting they may be enriched

454 for older haplotypes that contain multiple mutations that are under selection. However,
455 the opposite pattern was found for freshwater *A. macedonica*. No significant differences
456 were detected in the remaining three comparisons conducted.

457

458 *Genetic parallelism within and across lineages*

459 Parallelism was measured within *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*, and among all four
460 of the lineages examined. The percentage of shared outlier regions between pairs of
461 populations within *A. alosa* was generally lower (an average of 18%) than *A. f. lacustris*
462 (48%), as was it across all three populations in each lineage (Figure 3). However,
463 pairwise estimates within both species were generally several-fold higher than between
464 freshwater populations of any of the four lineages studied. The geographic/genetic
465 distance between the anadromous and freshwater populations studied in each lineage
466 makes it possible that some of the outlier regions identified were caused by selection due
467 to factors other than adapting to freshwater (e.g., temperature). Additionally, predicting
468 how neutral evolutionary history such as secondary contact will affect the number of
469 shared outlier regions among populations and lineages was not assessed. While these
470 issues do limit our study, congruence between our genome-wide analyses of parallelism
471 and that of *ATPase- $\alpha 1.1b$* (see below) provide support for our overall conclusions
472 regarding this topic.

473 Parallelism among lineages was then compared to the amount of shared
474 polymorphism between them. The percentage of polymorphism shared was highest for
475 the two subspecies examined, *A. f. lacustris* and *A. f. killarnensis* (64%), and lowest
476 between *A. alosa* and *A. macedonica* (25%) (Figure 3). Despite the subspecies examined

477 sharing from 30% to 50% more polymorphism than any of the other lineages, parallelism
478 was slightly higher for the two subspecies than in any of the cross-species comparisons.

479 In addition, only a fraction of the hundreds of thousands to millions of SNPs
480 found per lineage were shared by more than two lineages. For example, around 70
481 thousand shared SNP loci among the three naturally landlocked groups (*A. f. lacustris*, *A.*
482 *f. killarnensis*, and *A. macedonica*), and just several thousand SNPs were shared among
483 all four lineages of freshwater shad (see Supplemental Table 7). In several cases, the
484 same genomic region was found to be an outlier in three of the lineages (Supplemental
485 Figures 1 and 2; Supplemental Table 6). No genomic region was an outlier in all four of
486 the lineages studied.

487

488 *Evolutionary analysis of ATPase- $\alpha 1.1b$*

489 To help understand the genome-wide patterns of parallel genetic evolution
490 identified here, we focused on a gene that is likely to be a target of selection in the
491 lineages we studied, *ATPase- $\alpha 1.1b$* . First, phylogenetic analysis was used to infer the
492 orthology of all *ATPase- $\alpha 1$* identified in our study. Statistical support for most internal
493 nodes in the maximum likelihood trees generated for each gene was significant (>70%
494 bootstrap support; Supplemental Figure 7). The analysis revealed that the *ATPase- α*
495 found to be a top outlier in *A. f. lacustris* was likely *ATPase- $\alpha 1.3$* . It also confirmed
496 *ATPase- $\alpha 1.1b$* which was found to be a candidate gene in *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* was
497 an ortholog of the *ATPase- $\alpha 1$* identified as under selection in Velotta et al. 2017.

498 Among the mutations in *ATPase- $\alpha 1.1b$* with extreme ΔAF between anadromous
499 and freshwater populations of *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* were three that were

500 nonsynonymous. One of these three mutations, 67,614/968 (positions in Figure 4,5), was
501 an outlier in both *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* with ΔAF between 0.6 and 1.0 in two out of
502 three freshwater populations in each lineage, and a third exhibiting more moderate
503 changes (~ 0.3). In *A. alosa*, two additional nonsynonymous mutations in *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib*
504 that also exhibited extreme ΔAF (74,172/435 and 74,247/410) were found. To further
505 understand the statistical significance of the ΔAF estimate for the nonsynonymous
506 mutation in *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* shared by *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*, 67,614/968, we
507 examined the genome-wide distribution of ΔAF for all nonsynonymous mutations shared
508 by the two lineages. Among all nonsynonymous mutations shared by the two lineages,
509 67,614/968 in *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* had the highest combined ΔAF . It was also the only one
510 with ΔAF in the top 95th percentile of all ΔAF for all nonsynonymous mutations in each
511 *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*. All three nonsynonymous changes in *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* had
512 similar allele frequencies in all populations studied suggesting they may be part of the
513 same haplotype.

514 The functional consequences of these three nonsynonymous mutations were
515 explored using protein modeling and phylogenetic analysis. Based on our amino acid
516 alignment of *ATPase- $\alpha 1$* from a phylogenetically diverse set of fish species, each of the
517 three positions that had nonsynonymous mutations in *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* are moderately
518 conserved loci (Figure 5). The amino acid change at position 968 from Leucine (L) to
519 Phenylalanine (F) is nearby to an inserted or retained amino acid (position 967). This
520 insertion is absent in *ATPase- $\alpha 1$* of most fish species but found in a minority of copies of
521 the gene present in clupeids and other euryhaline fish such as some salmonids and
522 killifish. Protein modeling of the three nonsynonymous mutations indicated that the two

523 nonsynonymous mutations that were outliers in just *A. alosa* (positions 410 and 435 in
524 our amino acid alignment) are part of the same loop within the nucleotide-binding
525 domain, suggesting they may work in concert to alter how ATP binds to the protein
526 (Figure 5). The amino acid change shared by *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* (position 968)
527 was found to be in the cell membrane between the cytoplasm and extracellular regions
528 where it may affect ion transport.

529

530 **Discussion**

531 Here we studied the genomics of four lineages of anadromous Eurasian shad that
532 have evolved freshwater life histories. Our results show that adaptation to freshwater in
533 these alosines involved a combination of parallel and independent genetic changes.
534 Parallelism varied extensively at each of the two phylogenetic scales investigated but was
535 generally greater within lineages than among them.

536

537 *Parallelism within lineages*

538 Multiple freshwater populations exist for two of the four *Alosa* lineages we
539 studied (*A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*), making it possible to investigate parallelism within
540 each of these. The freshwater *A. alosa* studied here have only been diverging for tens of
541 generations. Our evidence for parallelism in *A. alosa* (Figure 3, Supplemental Text,
542 Supplemental Figure 2) adds to a growing body of literature showing that adaptation can
543 rapidly occur (Bell et al., 2004; Hairston et al., 2005). We also found support for
544 parallelism among freshwater populations of *A. f. lacustris*. Within *A. alosa* and *A. f.*
545 *lacustris*, genomic outlier regions common to all freshwater populations studied were

546 identified (i.e., “complete parallelism”). However, in *A. alosa*, complete parallelism was
547 less common than in *A. f. lacustris*.

548 Greater parallelism, overall, within *A. f. lacustris* than *A. alosa* is consistent with
549 freshwater *A. f. lacustris*: 1) having probably been founded by anadromous shad from the
550 same drainage (Sabatino et al., 2022), 2) potentially diverging with gene flow and not
551 being completely independent, and 3) inhabiting lakes with similar environments (e.g.,
552 temperature, water chemistry, and predators) (Salmaso et al., 2012; Salmaso & Mosello,
553 2010). In contrast, the freshwater *A. alosa* populations studied were each founded by
554 different anadromous ones just tens of generations ago and without gene flow. This
555 scenario resulted in parallelism within *A. alosa* that was less than found among the four
556 lineages examined but lower than in *A. f. lacustris*. Allele frequencies can take hundreds
557 of generations to reach equilibrium in response to selection (Star & Spencer, 2013). It is,
558 therefore, likely that lower parallelism in *A. alosa* is due at least in part to divergence
559 time. Additionally, the two freshwater populations with the highest number of shared
560 outlier regions were founded by the two (of the three involved) most closely related
561 anadromous ones (Sabatino et al., 2022). This suggests that within this lineage, in the
562 absence of gene flow, similarity in the gene pools of the founding populations can
563 increase the likelihood of parallelism. However, these freshwater populations are just
564 decades old, and allele frequencies for traits under selection due to their recent ecological
565 expansion may still be changing. Future studies should examine if and how parallelism
566 within *A. alosa* shifts over time to further test these hypotheses.

567

568 *Parallelism among lineages*

569 Our results indicate that parallelism among the lineages examined is not
570 widespread. No evidence for parallelism between lineages was found using our most
571 conservative statistical cutoff for identifying outlier genomic regions (99.9th percentile).
572 At the 99th percentile level, pairs of populations from different lineages shared less than
573 5% (hundreds) of their outlier regions (Figure 3). Fewer regions (from one to six) were
574 shared by sets of three lineages (Supplemental Table 6). Together, these results show that
575 adaptation to freshwater is often independent across these lineages. Of the millions of
576 SNPs that we identified across the four lineages here, the number common to all was in
577 the thousands. For each of the three lineages, this number was in the tens of thousands
578 (Supplemental Table 7). This makes it plausible that the (low) level of shared
579 polymorphism across the lineages examined is a limiting factor to parallelism.

580 If shared polymorphism promotes parallelism across these lineages, it should be
581 highest for *A. f. lacustris* and *A. f. killarnensis* since they are the most closely related of
582 the four examined. While this was found to be the case (Figure 3), the proportion of
583 overlapping regions shared between populations of each subspecies was only marginally
584 higher than between those of different species. While we cannot rule out bias in our
585 results due to the methods used to identify outlier regions and measure shared
586 polymorphism (e.g., coverage, sampling), and the low number of lineages examined, our
587 results suggest that shared polymorphism is not a strong driver of parallelism across these
588 four *Alosa* lineages. This hypothesis was supported by our focused analysis of parallelism
589 involving *ATPase- α .1b*

590

591 *Parallelism for ATPase- α*

592 Several lines of evidence indicated that *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* is under selection in *A.*
593 *alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*. Among the nucleotide sites in *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* that exhibited
594 extraordinary Δ AF in *A. alosa* were three nonsynonymous mutations, one of which also
595 sits at the tip of sharply peaked outlier regions in two of the three *A. f. lacustris*
596 populations (Supplemental Figure 2). This was also the only one of the three
597 nonsynonymous mutations found in outlier regions of both *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*.
598 Using protein modeling, this same mutation was predicted to change an amino acid that
599 affects a transmembrane domain of Na⁺/K⁺ATPase (Figure 5) and thus may play a
600 functional role in ion pumping. Lastly, *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* was shown to be orthologous to an
601 *ATPase- $\alpha 1$* that is differentially expressed in freshwater versus anadromous *A.*
602 *pseudoharengus* in common garden experiments involving osmotic stress (Velotta et al.,
603 2017). Combined, these results suggest that *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* is under selection in *Alosa*
604 species and that in *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* it involves protein-coding changes. Ion
605 transport involving ATPases is an active process that's efficiency can be affected by
606 temperature (Galarza-Munoz et al., 2011). Mismatches between *ATPase- $\alpha 1$,*
607 environmental conditions, and the migratory behaviors of shad may thus significantly
608 decrease the efficiency, or increase the energetic costs, of biological processes such as
609 osmoregulation, resulting in them being under natural selection in these lineages.

610 However, *ATPase- $\alpha 1$* are expressed in a variety of tissues and plays roles in other
611 biological processes that likely affect fitness in shad. For example, *ATPase- $\alpha 1$* are
612 involved in brain development in zebrafish (Doğanlı et al., 2013; Rajarao et al., 2001).
613 Functional assays to determine the fitness effects of the nonsynonymous mutations found
614 in *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.Ib* may help to characterize the selective forces acting on them in shad.

615 Despite the only two subspecies we examined, *A. f. lacustris* and *A. f. killarnensis*,
616 sharing the most polymorphism of any two lineages within our study, *ATPase- α 1.1b* was
617 not an outlier in *A. f. killarnensis*. Moreover, the nonsynonymous *ATPase- α 1.1b* alleles
618 found were not found in any of the populations (anadromous or freshwater) studied in the
619 *A. f. killarnensis* lineage. This provides a clear example of how the genetic distance and
620 overall shared polymorphism is not a good predictor of parallelism within these lineages.

621 The observed patterns of genetic evolution in *ATPase- α 1.1b* across populations
622 within *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* may provide some clues as to what may influence
623 parallelism in these lineages. Although the genomic regions that contained *ATPase- α 1.1b*
624 in *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* exhibited some of the most extreme Δ AF observed, such
625 changes were not consistently observed in all freshwater populations of each lineage
626 (Figure 4). The putatively freshwater adapted *ATPase- α 1.1b* allele for locus 67614/968
627 (Figure 4) was present in all six of these freshwater populations and so suggests that lack
628 of shared polymorphism is not the underlying cause of incomplete parallelism in these
629 cases. Partial parallelism here may have been driven by drift outweighing the effect of
630 selection in some populations. However, a lack of adaptive change due to the effects of
631 drift and/or weak selection would have had to occur independently in each lineage,
632 making it a less parsimonious explanation.

633 One alternative hypothesis is that antagonistic genetic interactions have shaped
634 the observed patterns in allele frequencies for *ATPase- α 1.1b* and/or genes linked to it.
635 Fitness tradeoffs and trait associations involving $\text{Na}^+ \text{K}^+$ -ATPase and osmoregulation and
636 migration have been identified in *Alosa* (Velotta et al., 2015; Zydlewski & McCormick,
637 1997) including *A. alosa* (Leguen et al., 2007), and other anadromous/freshwater species

638 like salmon (Hecht et al., 2013) and stickleback (Hohenlohe et al., 2010). A common
639 characteristic of loci experiencing antagonistic pleiotropy is that the polymorphisms
640 involved are under balancing selection polymorphisms in some ecological settings
641 (Connallon & Clark, 2012). Intermediate allele frequencies for SNPs in and around
642 *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.1b* were observed for both anadromous populations studied in the *A. alosa*
643 lineages, and one in the *A. f. lacustris*, exhibited, providing support for this hypothesis.

644 However, the high Δ AF for SNPs in other genes adjacent to *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.1b* such
645 as *Mk2* and *Axin1-like* (Figure 4) indicate that the evolution of this genomic region may
646 be more complicated. The allele frequencies for most SNPs in this region, including the
647 nonsynonymous ones *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.1b* and *Axin1-like*, had similar allele frequencies in
648 different populations, suggesting linkage disequilibrium among them and the potential
649 existence of a large, multi-gene haplotype that is under selection. Like *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.1b*,
650 *Axin1* is involved in brain development (Carl et al., 2007), making it plausible they are
651 under similar selection pressures. If so, the ultimate effects of selection in each lineage
652 may be difficult to predict (Hill & Robertson, 1966).

653 Indeed, genetic divergence (D_{XY}) was consistently higher within outlier regions
654 (including *ATPase- $\alpha 1$.1b*) identified in *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* (Supplemental Figures
655 2 and 6). This suggests that they are comprised of ancient haplotypes, as was found for
656 outlier regions in herring and stickleback (Martinez Barrio et al., 2016; Nelson & Cresko,
657 2018). In the case of *A. alosa*, this is likely the case given the populations were founded
658 just tens of generations ago, and little time has passed for new mutations to occur. In
659 herring, outlier regions also had elevated diversity (π), which was interpreted as them
660 containing multiple causal mutations (Martinez Barrio et al., 2016). This same pattern

661 was found for outlier regions in freshwater *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* (Supplemental
662 Figure 6b) suggesting they may contain haplotypes with multiple loci under natural
663 selection. The existence of several nonsynonymous mutations with extreme ΔAF in the
664 outlier region containing *ATPase- $\alpha 1.1b$* and *Axin1* supports this hypothesis.

665

666 *Parallelism in Eurasian shad and other species*

667 Parallelism within *A. alosa* and *A. f. lacustris* found here appears lower than in
668 stickleback and some strictly marine species but similar to that in other anadromous and
669 freshwater organisms. For example, a high degree of parallelism exists for multiple loci
670 across replicate populations of freshwater-adapted stickleback (Cresko et al., 2004;
671 Hohenlohe et al., 2010; Magalhaes et al., 2021). In the marine snail, *Littorina saxatilis*,
672 around 15% of outlier windows were shared among five or more pairs of populations of
673 ecotypes (Morales et al., 2019). And, in codfish and herring, genes involved in thermal
674 adaptation and reproduction timing, respectively, showed consistent signs of parallel
675 evolution (Bradbury et al., 2010; Lamichhaney et al., 2017). By contrast, like in *A.*
676 *alosa* and *A. f. lacustris*, complete parallelism in alewife (Velotta et al., 2017), salmonids
677 (Hecht et al., 2013; Jeffery et al., 2017), whitefish (Renaut et al., 2012), and cichlids
678 (Elmer et al., 2014; Meier et al., 2018), was rare. One set of factors that may help explain
679 these broadscale differences is that effective population size and genetic structure are
680 generally higher, and gene flow is lower, in anadromous species like shad, and those in
681 freshwater, compared to stickleback, whitefish, herring, and snails (Waples, 1998).
682 Indeed, at higher geographic scales (Fang et al., 2020, 2021; Magalhaes et al., 2021;
683 Roberts Kingman et al., 2021), and when N_E or genetic diversity is limited due to

684 historical factors (Dahms et al., 2022), parallelism in stickleback is more moderate than at
685 the regional or local scales.

686 However, the observed disconnect between parallelism and shared polymorphism
687 in the alosines studied here also highlights how the situation may often be more
688 complicated. One possible explanation is secondary contact. Introgressed alleles are
689 often involved in adaptation (Hedrick, 2013), and hybridization among contemporary
690 populations *A. alosa* and *A. fallax* has resulted in gene flow among them (Aprahamian et
691 al., 2003; Faria et al., 2012; Taillebois et al., 2019). If introgression from hybridization
692 occurred during the divergence of each lineage, our results indicate it was insufficient to
693 maintain a level of shared polymorphism that strongly promotes parallelism. However,
694 introgressed alleles under balancing selection will often have longer coalescence times
695 than neutral ones (Charlesworth et al. 1997). Introgression may have thus significantly
696 altered the geographic distribution of fitness-related alleles available for adaptation (and
697 parallelism) in these lineages. If introgressed alleles were often involved in adaptation to
698 freshwater in these lineages, then genetic distance or neutral shared polymorphism would
699 poorly predict patterns of parallelism, as has been found.

700 Parallelism across lineages may have also been limited by environmental factors.
701 Environmental similarity is a strong driver of parallelism in some species (Magalhaes et
702 al., 2021). While anadromous individuals colonized each freshwater location studied,
703 their life histories, phenotypes, and habitats in the Atlantic, Mediterranean, and Black Sea
704 are far from identical. At the same time, while the freshwater shad we studied tend to
705 phenotypically converge, they differ in some traits (e.g., size and parity) and inhabit
706 contrasting freshwater environments ranging from the alkaline lakes in the foothills of the

707 Italian Alps to recently formed reservoirs in Portugal. Accordingly, anadromous
708 individuals may have required lineage, or freshwater-habitat, specific genetic changes to
709 evolve a freshwater life history. It is also noteworthy that the freshwater *A. alosa* studied
710 adapted to a freshwater history in a single generation, serving as a remarkable example of
711 the well-known physiological flexibility and plasticity of the genus concerning their life
712 histories and osmoregulation (Aprahamian et al., 2003). This plasticity may have resulted
713 in weaker selection for traits that evolved in response to ecological changes experienced
714 by all freshwater populations in each lineage, such as osmoregulation in freshwater as
715 adults. If so, allele frequency changes resulting from lineage or drainage-specific
716 adaptations due to comparatively intense selective pressures may have often
717 overshadowed them in our analysis.

718

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729

730 **Data Accessibility:**

731 The DNA sequence data for the genome assembly and pooled-sequencing in this
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733 SAMN15659519). The genome annotation can be found at
734 <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.6djh9w13n>.

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739 **Authors' Contributions and Conflict of Interest:**

740 Designed research – Stephen J. Sabatino and Miguel Carneiro; Sampling - Stephen J.
741 Sabatino and Francesco Nonnis-Marzano; Performed research - Stephen J. Sabatino,

742 Paulo Pereira and Jolita Dilytė; Contributed new reagents or analytical tools - Stephen J.
743 Sabatino, Paulo Pereira, Jolita Dilytė and Antonio Murias; Analyzed data - Stephen J.
744 Sabatino and Paulo Pereira; Genome Assembly - Stephen J. Sabatino; Genome
745 Annotation - Stephen J. Sabatino, John Patrick Archer, Antonio Munoz; Wrote the paper
746 - Stephen J. Sabatino with extensive contributions from Paulo Pereira and editing from all
747 other authors. All authors approved the manuscript before submission declare that there is
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1173 Table 1. Statistics from the ALLPATHS genome assembly for *A. alosa*.
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Estimated genome size (bp)	889,386,068
Assembly size (bp)	876,687,730
Scaffold N50 (bp)	2,036,090
Contig N50 (bp)	9,900
Total contig length (bp)	621,125,889
# Scaffolds > 1000bp	15,886
Repeat content	36%
% GC content	43.4%
Heterozygosity	1/230
Protein-coding gene count	32,983

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1211 Table 2. The numbers of outlier windows (20 consecutive SNPs) and regions (outlier
 1212 windows within 20 kilobases of each other) per lineage and population(s) studied.
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Lineage	Population	99th percentile		99.9th percentile	
		Windows	Regions	Windows	Regions
<i>A. alosa</i>	All	1394	397	140	36
	Agueira Reservoir		398		37
	Castelo de Bode Reservoir		412		57
	Alqueva Reservoir		431		31
<i>A. f. lacustris</i>	All	1568	554	157	85
	Lake Maggiore		609		83
	Lake Como		556		77
	Lake Garda		581		79
<i>A. f. killarnensis</i>	Lough Leane	2173	552	218	70
<i>A. macedonica</i>	Lake Volvi	1428	491	143	70

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Figure 1. a): Map of sampling locations for the four lineages studied: *A. alosa* – Atlantic (Navy), *A. f. killarnensis* – Ireland (Green), *A. f. lacustris* – Italy (Orange), *A. macedonica* – Black Sea (Black). The name of each location sampled is as follows: 1– Garonne River, 2 – Mondego River, 3 – Aguieira Reservoir, 4 – Castelo de Bode Reservoir, 5 – Alqueva Reservoir, 6 – Tavignano River, 7 – Po River, 8 – Lake Maggiore, 9 – Lake Como, 10 – Lake Garda, 11 – Mondego River, 12 – Lima River, 13 – Lough Leane, 14 – Danube River – Tulcea, 15 – Danube River – Iron Gate, 16 – Lake Volvi. The locations marked by a square on the map are anadromous populations and those with a circle are freshwater. b): Phylogenetic tree of the populations studied based on genetic distance (F_{ST}). c): The map identification number (ID), species, sample size, and population history of each sample. d): A schematic of the experimental design used in this study.

Figure 2. Allele frequency differences (ΔAF) per genomic window between anadromous and freshwater populations of the four lineages studied: *A. alosa* – Atlantic (Navy), and *A. f. killarnensis* – Ireland (Green), *A. f. lacustris* – Italy (Orange), *A. macedonica* – Black Sea (Black). On the X-axis, the SNPs are ordered based on their position in each scaffold from our *A. alosa* genome assembly, with the largest scaffolds on the left and the smallest on the right. The Y-axis shows $-\log_{10}(P)$ values calculated using 1,000 permutations of the data per lineage. The horizontal lines indicate the 99.9th (black) and 99th (white) percentiles.

Figure 3. The percentage of polymorphism shared compared to the percentage of outlier regions (99th percentile) in common for pairs and sets of freshwater populations studied. The colored circles with numbers refer to populations as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 4. A heat map of allele frequencies for nonsynonymous mutations found in *ATPase- $\alpha 1.1b$* and *Axin1-like*. The number atop each column is the location of the SNP in scaffold_411 in our *A. alosa* genome assembly. At the end of each row is the name of the population and a symbol indicating if it is anadromous (squares) or freshwater (circles). Each cell is shaded grey based on the frequency of the "freshwater" allele.

Figure 5. A 3D-model of Na,K-ATPase and subsections of an amino acid alignment of *ATPase- α* from several fish species. In the alignment, the alternative alleles for the three protein coding changes found in freshwater populations of *A. alosa* are shown. In the protein model, the domains where these three mutations occur are highlighted in yellow (nucleotide-binding) and blue (transmembrane). The rest of *ATPase- α* is colored white while *ATPase- β* and *ATPase- γ* are both dark grey. The numbering of amino acid positions corresponds to that used in (Shinoda et al. 2009) for the spiny dogfish.

Table 1. Statistics from the ALLPATHS genome assembly for *A. alosa*.

Estimated genome size (bp)	889,386,068
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Total contig length (bp)	621,125,889
# Scaffolds > 1000bp	15,886
Repeat content	36%
% GC content	43.4%
Heterozygosity	1/230
Protein-coding gene count	32,983

Table 2. The numbers of outlier windows (20 consecutive SNPs) and regions (outlier windows within 20 kilobases of each other) per lineage and population(s) studied.

Lineage	Population	99th percentile		99.9th percentile	
		Windows	Regions	Windows	Regions
<i>A. alosa</i>	All	1394	397	140	36
	Aguieira Reservoir		398		37
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	Lake Maggiore		609		83
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	Lake Garda		581		79
<i>A. f. killarnensis</i>	Lough Leane	2173	552	218	70
<i>A. macedonica</i>	Lake Volvi	1428	491	143	70

Supplemental Figure 2. Plots of differences in allele frequencies (ΔAF) for genomic windows per population for all four lineages studied for several candidate genes identified in this study. The plots are colored as follows: *A. alosa* – Atlantic (Navy), *A. fallax* – Ireland (Green), *A. fallax* – Italy (Orange), and *A. macedonica* – Black Sea (Black). Triangles mark the location of each gene or pair of genes named at the top of each plot. The plot at the bottom of each row shows the median of the nucleotide diversity across the four lineages (π) in 20 kilobase windows with a step size of ten kilobases.

Supplemental Figure 3. Principle Components Analysis from PCadapt for two of the lineages studied. The numbered squares (anadromous) and circles (freshwater) are populations as shown in Figure 1.

Supplemental Figure 4. Manhattan plot of p-values for PCadapt (top of each panel) and allele frequency differences (ΔAF) per genomic window (bottom) between anadromous and freshwater populations of the four lineages studied: *A. alosa* – Atlantic (Navy), and *A. f. killarnensis* – Ireland (Green), *A. f. lacustris* – Italy (Orange), *A. macedonica* – Black Sea (Black). On the X-axis, the SNPs are ordered based on their position in each scaffold from our *A. alosa* genome assembly, with the largest scaffolds on the left and the smallest on the right.

Supplemental Figure 5. Phylogenetic tree of the ATPase genes for several fish species including *A. alosa*. Genes found in our *A. alosa* assembly are shaded grey. A star is used to mark ATPase genes found to be candidates in our genome scan analysis.

Supplemental Figure 6a and 6b. Comparisons of (a) absolute genetic divergence, D_{XY} , and (b) median nucleotide diversity, π , within (+) and outside (-) of outlier regions. The analysis of π was done separately for anadromous and freshwater populations within each of the four lineages. In each plot, significant differences between non-outlier and outlier regions are marked with an asterisk next to the lineage name.

(a)

(b)

Supplemental Figure 7. Tajima's D (b) in non-outlier (-) and outlier (+) genomic regions in each of the 16 populations studied. Measurements are the averages for 20kb windows across each type of region. Populations are shown by numbered squares (anadromous) and circles (freshwater) as indicated in Figure 1.

Supplemental Table 1. The sampling locations and size (“N”) of the anadromous and freshwater populations of *Alosa* studied. The sequencing coverage for each pool of individuals per population is given under (“CV”). Each species/lineage is colored according to the map distance tree in Figure 1. The estimates of genetic diversity provided are average π for 20 kilobase genomic windows. Locations with white circles next to them are freshwater populations that do not migrate to marine waters.

Species	Sampling Location	N	CV	π	Country	Drainage Basin	Latitude	Longitude
<i>A. alosa</i>	Garonne River	48	30	0.00212	France	Atlantic	45°36'06"N	01°04'07"W
<i>A. alosa</i>	Mondego River	32	37	0.00199	Portugal	Atlantic	40°08'44"N	08°51'44"W
<i>A. alosa</i>	○ Aguieira Reservoir	29	36	0.00198	Portugal	Atlantic	40°21'10"N	08°10'30"W
<i>A. alosa</i>	○ Castelo de Bode Reservoir	21	27	0.00194	Portugal	Atlantic	39°32'41"N	08°18'57"W
<i>A. alosa</i>	○ Alqueva Reservoir	66	39	0.00182	Portugal	Atlantic	38°12'39"N	07°28'49"W
<i>A. fallax</i>	Lima River	19	29	0.00316	Portugal	Atlantic	41°41'09"N	08°49'57"W
<i>A. fallax</i>	Mondego River	11	33	0.00328	Portugal	Atlantic	40°08'44"N	08°51'44"W
<i>A. f. killarnensis</i>	○ Lough Leane	43	36	0.00263	Ireland	Atlantic	52°02'22"N	09°33'47"W
<i>A. fallax</i>	Tavignano River	15	24	0.00249	France	Mediterranean	42°06'13"N	09°32'58"E
<i>A. fallax</i>	Po River	20	26	0.00239	Italy	Mediterranean	44°57'12"N	12°25'56"E
<i>A. f. lacustris</i>	○ Lake Maggiore	14	28	0.0019	Italy	Mediterranean	45°59'02"N	08°40'29"E
<i>A. f. lacustris</i>	○ Lake Como	39	33	0.00194	Italy	Mediterranean	45°59'17"N	09°14'43"E
<i>A. f. lacustris</i>	○ Lake Garda	33	44	0.00198	Italy	Mediterranean	45°34'30"N	10°38'11"E
<i>A. immaculata</i>	Danube River - Tulcea	40	37	0.00279	Serbia	Black/Adriatic Seas	45°12'48"N	28°47'04"E
<i>A. immaculata</i>	Danube River - Iron Gate	25	26	0.00266	Romania	Black/Adriatic Seas	44°40'1"N	22°31'55"E
<i>A. macedonica</i>	○ Lake Volvi	12	31	0.00221	Greece	Black/Adriatic Seas	40°40'58"N	23°28'27"E

Supplemental Table 2. The Genbank accession number or gene model name of all sequences used for phylogenetic analysis of ATPase- α 1 is provided.

ATPase		
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1a1a	NM_131686.1	α 1.1
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1a.4	NM_131689.1	α 1.1
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1a.5	NM_178099.2	α 1.1
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1a.3	NM_131688.1	α 1.1
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1a.2	NM_131687.1	α 1.1
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1a.1b	NM_131690.1	α 1.1
<i>Alosa alosa</i> - α 1.1a	Allis_9072	α 1.1
<i>Alosa pseudoharengus</i> - α 1.1a	GFCK01198590.1	α 1.1
<i>Clupea harengus</i> - α 1.1a	XM_012815450.1	α 1.1
<i>Alosa pseudoharengus</i> - α 1.1b	GFCK01208951.1	α 1.1
<i>Alosa alosa</i> - α 1.1b	GETY01052870	α 1.1
<i>Alosa alosa</i> - α 1.2	Allis_124	α 1.2
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1.2a	NM_131683.1	α 1.2
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1.3b	AY008374.1	α 1.3
<i>Danio rerio</i> - α 1.3a	NM_131684.2	α 1.3
<i>Alosa alosa</i> - α 1.3	GETY01025548.1	α 1.3
<i>Clupea harengus</i> - α 1.3a	XM_012819956	α 1.3
<i>Clupea harengus</i> - α 1.3b	XM_012818286.1	α 1.3
<i>Xenopus tropicalis</i> - nongastric-HKA	NM_001087349.1	nongastric
<i>Mus musculus</i> - nongastric-HKA	NM_138652.2	nongastric
<i>Homo sapien</i> - α 1.4	GQ891529.1	α 1.4
<i>Mus musculus</i> - gastric-HKA	NM_001290627.1	gastric
<i>Xenopus tropicalis</i> - gastric-HKA	NM_001090874.1	gastric

Supplemental Table 3. The Genbank accession numbers for the amino acid sequences used in the ATPase- α 1 protein alignment are shown.

Species	Accession/Transcript
Annual killifish	XP_013874891
Mozambique tilapia	KC702514
Atlantic salmon	BT058747
Three-spined stickleback	BT027976
Atlantic herring	XP_012673740
Allis shad -Allele 1	GETY01052870
Allis shad -Allele 2	GETY01052870
Alewife	GFCK01208951
Milkfish	XP_030634863
W. Indian ocean coelacanth	XM_014491963
Japanese eel	KU976439
Spotted gar	XP_006639434.1
Spiny dogfish	2ZZE_A

Supplemental Table 4. Statistics on SNP loci and genomic windows for each of the four lineages studied. The number of bi-allelic SNP loci, the number of SNP loci used per genome window, the number of genome windows examined, and the average size of genome windows per lineage are provided.

	Number SNPs	SNP/ Win.	Interval (N. SNPs)	Number of Win.	Avg. Win. Size (bp)
<i>A. alosa</i>	1407776	20	10	139329	10833
<i>A. f. lacustris</i>	1581898	20	10	156753	9649
<i>A. f. killarnensis</i>	2187475	20	10	217296	6996
<i>A. macedonica</i>	1441886	20	10	142732	10573

Supplemental Table 5. Annotations for all outlier genomic windows (99.9th percentile) for each lineage. The lineage to which the outlier windows belong is at the top of each section. The header “Sca.” is an abbreviation for “scaffold” and “pca” for PCadap. Outlier windows with and asterisk underneath “pca” were also outliers in our PCadap analysis.

Sca.	Start	Stop	Genes	pca	Sca.	Start	Stop	Genes	pca	Sca.	Start	Stop	Genes	pca
<i>A. alosa</i>					<i>A. alosa</i> (continued)					<i>A. f. lucasius</i> (continued)				
0	7439629	7440270		*	276	395269	404764	MOB4, DNAJB11; bcced1; Lemf.	*	52	3326297	3330040		*
0	7440126	7440903		*	301	45886	53495	gpr37	*	62	65080	70912		*
0	10601563	10604842		*	301	49329	58609		*	65	1724405	1728229	EH28_11885	*
0	10625420	10628024		*	391	196	5373		*	70	2402399	2404079		*
0	10627045	10631443		*	411	42	27186		*	70	2418032	2420333	ARRD3,	*
1	3176353	3182350		*	411	7648	29086		*	70	2419702	2422348	ARRD3,	*
1	3179793	3203258		*	411	64592	69982	Mkr2; ATP1A3	*	70	2420487	2422979	ARRD3,	*
1	9699734	9710961		*	411	67531	72507	Mkr2; ATP1A3	*	70	2422371	2424927	ARRD3,	*
1	9706137	9711700		*	411	70349	76203	Mkr2; ATP1A3	*	70	2423092	2429890	ARRD3,	*
3	1330847	1332673		*	411	73143	80389	Mkr2; ATP1A3	*	70	2431631	2435291		*
3	1332120	1334391		*	411	76271	82912	ATP1A3	*	70	2433508	2437555		*
3	1332723	1335758		*	411	80783	85134	ATP1A3	*	70	2435889	2439255		*
3	1334549	1337472		*	411	83128	86466	ATP1A3	*	70	2496091	2497996		*
3	1337692	1339956		*	411	85143	92558	ATP1A3; Thumpd1	*	70	2497077	2502975		*
3	1339123	1340584		*	411	92853	100734	Thumpd1	*	80	878476	885012		*
6	4639118	4646289	GP113; Ankrd66	*	411	99353	101621	Thumpd1	*	80	992166	1002986		*
6	4642674	4648714	GP113; Ankrd66	*	411	100828	103361	Thumpd1	*	80	1900073	1929136		*
10	3719989	3722510	impact	*	411	101639	104234	Thumpd1	*	82	2262993	2276983	DDX12P, FPR1	*
11	1700525	1720311	RICS; rbm42	*	411	103383	105526	Thumpd1	*	82	2274037	2278614		*
11	1716630	1723346	RICS; rbm42	*	411	104324	106789	Thumpd1	*	83	630071	634788	dre12, rergl	*
11	1720870	1726696	rbm42	*	411	105635	107261	Thumpd1	*	83	632215	636018	rergl	*
11	1723451	1729659	rbm42	*	411	106840	108807	Thumpd1	*	84	2124290	2132270	DEAF1, bet1l, IRK11, CD59, Pfdm1	*
11	1726875	1745473	rbm42	*	411	107289	110560	Thumpd1	*	87	1841272	1844949		*
11	1738092	1746887	rbm42	*	411	108943	116178	Thumpd1	*	87	1844184	1846161		*
11	1745526	1749532		*	411	110568	123737	Thumpd1; axin	*	87	1845133	1848880		*
11	1746894	1767204		*	411	116196	125761	Thumpd1; axin	*	103	480665	410647	fadl1, stap2	*
11	3459236	3463066	rpz3	*	411	123815	129396	axin	*	103	421630	425040	stap2, endo	*
11	3460038	3467151	rpz3; rpz5;	*	411	125804	133263	axin; AXIN1	*	106	1517162	1522122	ghrh	*
11	3486689	3494276	rpz5; rpz3; zgc:174938	*	411	129448	137367	axin; AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	114	345578	351074	SK2L2, wun	*
11	3490723	3532418	rpz3; zgc:174938; zgc:174938	*	411	133328	139260	axin; AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	114	349510	354402	SK2L2, wun	*
21	3066294	3071439	CDC47; amhr2;	*	411	137727	140327	axin; AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	114	354457	358978	SK2L2, wun	*
31	699786	716896	BCL11A	*	411	141503	144431	axin; AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	121	39229	49781	midn	*
31	714778	727434	BCL11A	*	411	143227	145250	axin; AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	122	9644	14256	Bco2, sor1l	*
32	2153626	2161927	MFAP4; C22orf9;	*	411	144561	145793	axin; AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	122	12299	17457	Bco2, sor1l	*
71	487806	491162	kbp	*	411	145266	146522	axin; AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	124	1567114	1575054	ATNA	*
73	2640757	2661261	camta1; camta1	*	411	145808	146798	axin; AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	124	1573102	1578718	ATNA	*
73	2656665	2665848	camta1; camta1	*	411	146565	148478	AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	125	10868	13862		*
73	2661614	2672923	camta1; camta1; camta1	*	411	146962	149680	AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	125	54715	83013		*
73	2666575	2686330	camta1; camta1; camta1	*	411	148517	156264	AXIN1; GTF3C1	*	125	83088	86998		*
73	2673221	2719648	camta1; camta1	*	669	63703	73810		*	125	85764	89075		*
101	2053963	2055437		*	<i>A. f. lucasius</i>					128	69077	73086		*
109	822671	825823	nih1; ITIH3	*	0	394	8043		*	140	1541747	1544593		*
109	823865	827279	nih1; ITIH3	*	1	5115272	5117731		*	140	1544319	1546162		*
109	825828	828130	nih1; ITIH3	*	3	5541029	5544950	MAB21L1	*	158	772632	780428		*
109	827664	829872	nih1; ITIH3	*	3	5543907	5546433	MAB21L1	*	187	534923	537261	ORSASI	*
109	828215	831976	nih1; ITIH3	*	3	5544952	5547806	MAB21L1	*	193	1137500	1142009		*
109	837609	842344	ITIH3	*	3	5557184	5566009	MAB21L1	*	195	348872	364509	SRF,	*
114	1036662	1040372	cna; SHTR	*	3	5559876	5567624	MAB21L1	*	195	1099026	1104307		*
114	1040634	1046243	SHTR	*	5	1706751	1713852	aur	*	195	1102458	1105078		*
114	1043899	1048106	SHTR	*	5	4130226	4133944	v1g108621, Myof	*	195	1104370	1108306		*
114	1046376	1050097	SHTR	*	7	2771427	2777722	TTC15, tucsl	*	226	758809	764726	CASC3	*
114	1048184	1058385	SHTR	*	10	5951993	5965922	opa1	*	228	763314	770047		*
114	1060850	1065655	DMTN	*	10	5962555	5968573		*	253	925742	928817		*
114	1077497	1080273	DMTN; An04g03700	*	11	644881	650136		*	254	59506	61661	Gk5	*
114	1078930	1082480	DMTN; An04g03700	*	11	648017	651009		*	255	199805	203834		*
114	1080316	1086538	DMTN; An04g03700; XPO7	*	11	650181	652967		*	257	737588	742758	APMAP, RASSF3	*
114	1082488	1089069	DMTN; An04g03700; XPO7	*	11	651209	655390		*	257	743031	748069	APMAP, RASSF3	*
114	1105132	1108275	XPO7; DOK3	*	11	653097	660108	thsd7a	*	259	109919	113574	IL1RL2	*
114	1106359	1109410	XPO7; DOK3	*	11	655627	662025	thsd7a	*	259	120595	129421	IL1RL2, CNOT8	*
114	1109483	1112547	XPO7; DOK3	*	11	688260	691873	thsd7a	*	259	123975	129956	CNO18	*
114	1111166	1113691	XPO7; DOK3	*	14	2358666	2360926	HCN1	*	259	129425	135216	CNO18	*
123	352935	355467	smyd5	*	14	2348899	2350650	HCN1	*	259	155019	160655	COX7B	*
123	354568	357039	smyd5	*	14	2350020	2353848	HCN1	*	259	162550	173799	COX7B, rpsL	*
123	386979	390881	Sfxn5; cryba1; cryba11l	*	14	2354234	2357736	HCN1	*	259	164668	175482	COX7B, rpsL	*
123	389849	392440	Sfxn5; cryba1; cryba11l	*	14	2356415	2360035	HCN1	*	259	173935	176917	COX7B, rpsL	*
126	1239564	1242853	RHG19	*	14	2358029	2362685	HCN1	*	292	571767	580337		*
126	1303529	1307152		*	15	2675935	2681381		*	292	579165	589108		*
126	1305762	1309251		*	15	4636940	4642514		*	303	64890	86787	CCKAR, cckar	*
126	1307259	1324651		*	19	2238940	2242121		*	303	99511	112764	PDZK1, GPR89A	*
126	1309338	1325946		*	24	3646541	3649902	SPHK2, CNOT3	*	303	106330	116354	PDZK1, GPR89A	*
126	1360050	1366468	abcc2	*	24	3648489	3652997	SPHK2, CNOT3	*	348	39101	49610		*
126	1366542	1368779	abcc2	*	29	1430339	1435650		*	353	56286	66855		*
126	1368276	1370616	abcc2	*	30	689579	698123		*	363	355092	383484	GSONMT00029675001, anf1	*
140	1236381	1240547		*	30	692383	714736		*	365	294447	295846	NLRC	*
140	1262971	1268876		*	32	1020462	1022566		*	378	77425	94796		*
140	1264394	1270191		*	33	1192988	1195851		*	378	166928	170282		*
140	1268915	1272643		*	33	1194423	1197595		*	378	217008	235293		*
141	204755	209170	Ubxn4; LOC704; GS01; NMI	*	34	2693655	2697733	gstt1, rbm19	*	378	239791	245754		*
141	207087	210376	Ubxn4; LOC704; GS01; NMI	*	35	450000	453291	CYTH4	*	378	260417	265280		*
141	209183	213326	Ubxn4; LOC704; GS01; NMI	*	35	452125	453799	CYTH4	*	378	262796	269541		*
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Supplemental Table 5 (continued). Annotations for all outlier gene windows (99.9th percentile) for each lineage. The lineage to which the outlier windows belong is at the top of each section. The header “Sca.” is an abbreviation for “scaffold” and “pca” for PCadapt. Outlier windows with and asterisk underneath “pca” were also outliers in our PCadapt analysis.

Sca	Start	Stop	Genes	pca	Sca	Start	Stop	Genes	pca	Sca	Start	Stop	Genes	pca
<i>A. f. kilarensis</i>					<i>A. f. kilarensis</i> (continued)					<i>A. macedonica</i> (continued)				
0	3308977	3311965	arrdc3, hfe2, thbs3a	*	107	117034	122009	pif1	*	29	378764	382769	aes	*
1	3310859	3313466	g2e1	*	107	126772	129125	elov11a	*	29	406860	412370	aes, EGR1, pvr4	*
6	6440658	6442986	SELL, janA	*	107	302677	304881	APS4	*	29	410628	414560	aes, EGR1, pvr4	*
10	145120	148558		*	107	568159	569680	AIMP1, TBCK	*	29	469264	471360		*
13	2218179	2225906	KCNT1	*	107	591329	594076	AIMP1, TBCK	*	29	476300	478491	cdh6	*
13	3258687	3262376	IAK3	*	107	593407	594719	TBCK	*	29	477735	481393	cdh6	*
14	4234215	4238649	acs5s, cdc124	*	107	598243	600146	TBCK	*	29	481856	485839	cdh6	*
14	4267756	4270639	CLCN7	*	107	599108	602358	TBCK	*	29	484246	488295	cdh6	*
16	4925959	4929085	CC3, beo1	*	107	600203	603831	TBCK	*	29	565560	572002	cdh6	*
17	3073316	3091673	hd	*	107	602422	606523	TBCK	*	30	1580436	1587635		*
20	4608633	4611865		*	107	606597	609776	TBCK	*	38	2764908	2769489	RPAP1	*
20	4746506	4754143		*	107	608638	616209	TBCK, LOXE3	*	38	2766454	2773728	RPAP1	*
20	4751986	4756097		*	107	636708	644262	LOXE3	*	38	2782596	2788731		*
20	4754617	4758472		*	107	648178	655253		*	39	741459	760732	astm1, *	
25	4631586	4635901		*	117	681907	687302		*	39	752639	767389	astm1, *, PAPP1	
25	4635068	4636755		*	123	725760	729781		*	42	2406475	2410034	CYP11B1, rmdh2	
25	4636327	4637885		*	125	148976	151867		*	43	294376	299196	tmx4	
25	4636810	4638361		*	125	149584	153806	myt1bb	*	43	2192524	2190254	sm4	
25	4637918	4639412		*	131	678478	684675	myt1bb	*	44	1837819	1842780	mnt11bb	
28	3880263	3884479		*	131	682639	686391	myt1bb	*	44	1847854	1849213	mnt11bb	
28	3881823	3888449		*	131	684972	688853	myt1bb	*	47	400832	402474	arhgap6	
28	3888649	3892719		*	131	686776	690242	myt1bb	*	47	3087458	3092015	gna1	
28	3891395	3895570		*	131	688886	691588	myt1bb	*	50	3422739	3424163	NPL0C4, PUPP451, RN213	
28	3892861	3904054		*	131	690600	693026	myt1bb	*	50	3423419	3424373	NPL0C4, PUPP451, RN213	
28	3895377	3908303		*	131	691611	694417	myt1bb	*	50	3424237	3424642	PPUP451, RN213	
28	3987952	3998886		*	131	693237	696441	myt1bb	*	51	2350654	2354153	ar1, cav3	
28	4012445	4017939	ZFP2, cdc34a	*	131	694615	698731	tmod2	*	54	254058	256025		
29	150557	152082	ZFP2, cdc34a	*	153	1249588	1252700	ATL3	*	54	2251333	2256330	HERC2	
29	151258	153242	hal1	*	158	678327	679811		*	54	2260234	2265831	HERC2	
29	2623737	2632402	mnt11aa	*	179	942803	943741		*	54	2262703	2267619		
29	2689574	2692250	mnt11aa	*	205	733705	734996	argG	*	54	2265835	2269013		
29	2690422	2693981		*	211	30258	35535		*	54	2267795	2269800		
29	2735988	2749115		*	213	345403	346928		*	54	2272997	2276832		
29	2755005	2759691	s100v2	*	215	681117	704700	plr, LOC100145344, T22D2						
29	2718429	2723607		*	218	469364	485063	PN2, PN2						
33	2720548	2724549	tc33, PTGER4	*	218	483426	487945	T22D2, PEN2						
40	1640746	1645094	tc33, PTGER4	*	218	488107	496526	T22D2, PEN2, absg, *						
40	1646327	1649756		*	218	490684	502146	T22D2, PEN2, absg, CRB1						
41	982605	986827	ergic1, flt4	*	218	496831	504459	PN2, absg, CRB1						
44	1379605	1384275		*	218	502979	505495	PN2, absg, CRB1						
48	1510362	1516207	KHSRP	*	218	504585	508405	PN2, absg, CRB1						
48	1530864	1535318	GSTENG00019343001	*	218	505759	509550	PN2, absg, CRB1						
48	1565124	1570084	GSTENG00019343001	*	218	508420	510407	absg, CRB1, ZBTB41						
48	1567912	1571165	GSTENG00019343001	*	218	510613	516000	absg, CRB1, ZBTB41						
48	1570557	1573376	cdc43	*	218	520312	525386	CRB1, ZBTB41						
48	1671883	1680767	PIEZO2	*	218	523853	528426	trve2, rgs1, rgs1						
48	1857798	1862124	PIEZO2	*	218	620660	623498							
48	1860615	1863383	PIEZO2	*	246	749920	752344							
48	1862142	1864264		*	246	751514	753093							
48	1894337	1897349		*	246	767258	770123	exon1, PHYHIP1L						
48	1898874	1904855		*	272	393605	397412	exon1, PHYHIP1L						
48	1914504	1919324		*	272	405363	407570	exon1, PHYHIP1L						
48	1923487	1925864		*	272	410212	414083	LRC8A, Ppil3, sdcag3						
48	1924756	1927707		*	324	235599	238236	LRC8A, Ppil3, sdcag3						
48	1926194	1930064		*	324	236613	239764	card9, SNPC4						
48	1927794	1933819		*	324	343216	346750	sich211-163c2.1						
48	1930094	1936404		*	324	342944	348613	zgc:171695						
48	1933911	1937685		*	324	347199	357572	zgc:171695						
48	1936455	1939475		*	324	348922	357875	zgc:171695						
48	1937822	1941007	lmpa2	*	324	357965	357975							
48	1945221	1948577	lmpa2	*	344	443106	448029							
48	1947130	1950613	lmpa2, mppc1	*	344	463819	467981							
48	1961553	1966803	lmpa2, mppc1	*	344	477996	485803							
48	1964655	1968220	lmpa2, mppc1	*	348	75908	78956							
48	1968284	1973449	lmpa2, mppc1	*	348	77132	85796	IR10, IR10						
48	1971952	1975825	lmpa2, mppc1	*	358	120085	128067	cntm7						
48	1973534	1977578	lmpa2, mppc1	*	373	150727	154872	frt07						
48	1976026	1980225	mppc1	*	452	14733	18665	frt07						
48	1977705	1983761	mppc1	*	452	18076	19598	myt1bb						
48	1980237	1986809	gna1	*	501	89392	95550	flxo41						
48	1993707	2005139	gna1	*	534	105768	112804	flxo41						
48	2000234	2006573	gna1	*	534	111752	115230	flxo41						
48	2005160	2009133	gna1	*	534	112843	117532	flxo41						
48	2006611	2011893	gna1	*	534	115712	121082	flxo41						
48	2009236	2014400	gna1	*	534	116499	122105	flxo41						
48	2011973	2017660	gna1	*	534	121088	123844	flxo41, cyp17a, *						
48	2014527	2019218	gna1	*	534	124411	129403	flxo41, cyp17a						
48	2017742	2023725	gna1	*	534	126107	131304	flxo41, cyp17a						
48	2019419	2028074	gna1	*	534	129649	132746	flxo41, cyp17a						
48	2024135	2033383		*	534	131357	134809	flxo41, cyp17a						
48	2024816	2042897	Elow2	*	534	132821	136924	flxo41, cyp17a						
48	2040295	2057174	Elow2	*	534	134843	138919	flxo41, cyp17a						
48	2043102	2060847	Elow2	*	534	137021	141047	flxo41, cyp17a, olge8						
48	2060876	2067476	Elow2	*	534	138947	144079	cyp17a, olge8						
48	2065684	2069974	Elow2	*	534	141099	146290	olge8, dcx, dcx1						
48	2067628	2075012	Elow2	*	534	170163	173332	dcx, dcx1						
48	2070191	2076786	Elow2	*	534	175984	184810	dcx, dcx1						
48	2075402	2084474	Elow2	*	534	181391	192020	fn1						
48	2076949	2086307		*	537	109003	117894							
48	2084505	2089127	gem2	*	540	172772	175783							
48	2086728	2092254	gem2	*	566	156809	171225							
48	2093238	2094471	gem2	*	566	170498	171685							
48	2092370	2098621	gem2	*	566	171250	172464							
48	2094638	2101272	gem2	*	566	171731	173271							
48	2099220	2105948	gem2	*	627	12546	14264							
48	2101523	2108596	gem2	*	627	13769	26962							
48	2106930	2112148		*	627	14289	28792							
48	2124598	2130619	nak, tmem4c	*	<i>A. macedonica</i>									
48	2144594	2156723	cdt1, aprt	*	0	9528512	9535343		*					
61	1542568	1544596		*	0	9582207	9584260	LIMS1	*					
62	1030577	1037092	cxcr1	*	5	5866889	5870992	EH29, 04093, Ppno, mrpl10, ospb7						
62	1038625	1042313	cxcr1	*	8	1996305	1997937	SWI1C, ac7, asmt						
62	1040523	1046289		*	8	1996987	1999426	SWAHC, Xc7, asmt						
65	2542665	2546329	cpnA	*	8	5361848	5364298							
65	2544094	2550385	cpnA	*	8	5363523	5365095							
65	2546585	2551823		*	8	5364338	5368218							
75	524445	562395		*	8	6496937	6502986	OSBP1L6, prkra						
75	27832	307226		*	8	6499946	6505099	OSBP1L6, prkra, *						
82	2160522	2168618		*	14	1467574	1474861	lrc16b						
82	2161339	2169816		*	14	1481136	1489426	maf, rem2						
82	2168629	2174652	siz	*	14	1486147	1491833	maf, rem2						
82	2174826	2178798	siz	*	14	1557509	1563126	vri						
82	2183225	2190187		*	23	191	4184	ZPS, ap1g2						
83	920269	923086	GMEB1	*	23	2334	7548	ZPS, ap1g2						
86	1899409	1915652	GMEB1, rab42a	*	24	301808	307234	PRSS35, IAN1						
86	1928016	1931602	GMEB1, rab42a	*	26	256957	259543	SLC26A2						
86	19302													

Supplemental Table 6. The number of outlier windows found using the Δ AF method and the number found using PCadapt. The percentage of outlier windows shared between the Δ AF method and PCadapt are shown.

	Outlier Windows			Δ AF - PCadapt	
	Δ AF		PCA		
	0.1	0.01	FDR	0.1	0.01
<i>A. alosa</i>	140	1,394	10,606	93%	85%
<i>A. f. lacustris</i>	157	1,568	7,618	89%	79%
<i>A. f. killarnensis</i>	218	2,173	6,409	75%	57%
<i>A. macedonica</i>	143	1,428	5,595	100%	89%

Supplemental Table 7. a) The number of shared polymorphic SNP loci between pairs of lineages and the average genetic distances (F_{ST}) between them. b) The shared number of SNP loci for the three naturally occurring lineages, and for all four studied. In each case, the percentage of polymorphism that is shared for each lineage is given in parentheses.

(a)

		Shared SNPs	F_{ST}
<i>A. macedonica</i> (4.3%)	<i>A. alosa</i> (4.4%)	61975	0.741
<i>A. f. lacustris</i> (6.5%)	<i>A. macedonica</i> (7.1%)	161406	0.707
<i>A. f. lacustris</i> (10.2%)	<i>A. alosa</i> (11.5%)	102105	0.746
<i>A. macedonica</i> (8.1%)	<i>A. f. killarnensis</i> (5.3%)	116340	0.648
<i>A. alosa</i> (29%)	<i>A. f. killarnensis</i> (18.7%)	408932	0.597
<i>A. f. lacustris</i> (26.3%)	<i>A. f. killarnensis</i> (19%)	415927	0.420

(b)

			Shared SNPs
<i>A. alosa</i> (4.92%)	<i>A. f. lacustris</i> (4.38%)	<i>A. f. killarnensis</i> (3.17%)	69241
<i>A. alosa</i> (1.41%)	<i>A. f. lacustris</i> (1.25%)	<i>A. macedonica</i> (1.37%)	19803
<i>A. alosa</i> (1.95%)	<i>A. f. killarnensis</i> (1.26%)	<i>A. macedonica</i> (1.91%)	27510
<i>A. f. lacustris</i> (4.38%)	<i>A. f. killarnensis</i> (3.17%)	<i>A. macedonica</i> (4.80%)	69241
<i>A. alosa</i> (0.62%)	<i>A. f. lacustris</i> (0.55%)	<i>A. f. killarnensis</i> (0.40%)	<i>A. macedonica</i> (0.61%) 8749

Supplemental Table 8. The outlier regions that overlapped among sets of three lineages in the first column are shown.

Lineages	Scaffold	Position	Genes
<i>A. alosa</i> / <i>A. f. lacustris</i> / <i>A. macedonica</i>	3	3147751:3153632	FOXO1
<i>A. alosa</i> / <i>A. f. lacustris</i> / <i>A. f. killarnensis</i>	1	3286046:3290803	ANKRD34A POLR3GL arrdc3
	43	2565039:2579150	
	171	201666:236147	nan bcap29 SO1C1 PDE3A
	411	131261:149447	axin AXIN1 GTF3C1
<i>A. alosa</i> / <i>A. f. killarnensis</i> / <i>A. macedonica</i>	57	2493888:2540054	S35B3 S35B3
	114	1002077:1027832	TC1 nan cna 5HT7R
<i>A. f. lacustris</i> / <i>A. f. killarnensis</i> / <i>A. macedonica</i>	8	6390750:6429471	ADAS pde5a
	29	2692135:2746969	mtnr1aa
	35	428534:450407	eif3d cuta sstr3 CYTH4
	48	1283295:1291952	Adap2 rhot1a C17orf75 znf207
	78	2523528:2523719	
	566	118694:159974	cbln5 C1Q